

BENCZE MIHÁLY
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About Bernoulli's Numbers

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About Bernoulli's Numbers¹

Many methods to compute the sum of the same powers of the first n natural numbers (see ([4]) are well-known.

In this paper we present a simple proof of the method from [3].

The Bernoulli's numbers are defined by

$$(1) \quad B_n = \frac{-1}{n+1} \left(C_{n-1}^0 B_0 + C_{n-1}^1 B_1 + \dots + C_{n-1}^{n-1} B_{n-1} \right)$$

where $B_0 = 1$. It is known that $B_{n-1} = 0$ if $n \geq 1$. By calculation we find that

$$(2) \quad B_1 = -1/2, B_2 = 1/6, B_4 = -1/30, B_6 = 1/42, B_8 = -1/30, B_{10} = 5/66, \\ B_{12} = -691/2730, B_{14} = 7/6, B_{16} = -3617/510, B_{18} = 43867/798, \\ B_{20} = -174611/330, B_{22} = 854513/138, B_{24} = -236364091/2730 \text{ etc.}$$

Let $S_n^k = 1^k + 2^k + \dots + n^k$ sum of the first n natural numbers which have the same power.

Theorem.

$$(3) \quad S_n^k = \frac{1}{k+1} \left(n^{k+1} + \frac{1}{2} C_{k+1}^1 n^k + C_{k+1}^2 B_2 n^{k-1} + \dots + C_{k+1}^k B_k n \right)$$

Proof. (1) can be written as:

$$(4) \quad \sum_{i=0}^n C_{n+1}^i B_i = 0, \quad n \geq 1.$$

$$\text{If } P(x) = \sum_{i=0}^k C_{k+1}^i B_i x^{k+1-i}, \quad \text{then } P(n+1) - P(n) = \\ = \sum_{i=0}^k C_{k+1}^i B_i \left((n+1)^{k+1-i} - n^{k+1-i} \right) = \\ = \sum_{i=0}^k C_{k+1}^i B_i \left(\sum_{j=1}^{k+1-i} C_{k+1-i}^j n^{k+1-i-j} \right).$$

Let A_i be the coefficients of n^{k-i} , where $i \in \{0, 1, \dots, k\}$.

$$A_i = \sum_{t=0}^i C_{k+1}^i C_{k+1-i}^{i-t+1} B_t = C_{k+1}^{i-1} \left(\sum_{t=0}^i C_{k+1-i}^t B_t \right).$$

If $t \geq 1$, then $A_i = 0$, only $A_0 = C_{k+1}^1$. On behalf of these

$$P(n+1) - P(n) = C_{k+1}^1 n^k. \text{ Using this}$$

$$\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} i^k = \frac{1}{k+1} \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (P(i+1) - P(i)) = \frac{1}{k+1} P(n),$$

¹Together with Mihály Bencze

because $P(0) = 0$. Then $S_n^k = \frac{1}{k+1} P(n) + n^k$. From here one gets (3).

Note. From the previous result we can also find the formula

$$S_n^k = \frac{1}{k+1} P(n+1).$$

Using the previous, we find the next equalities:

$$S_n^0 = n, S_n^1 = \frac{1}{2} n(n+1), S_n^2 = \frac{1}{6} n(n+1)(2n+1), S_n^3 = \frac{1}{4} n^2(n+1)^2,$$

$$S_n^4 = \frac{1}{30} n(n+1)(2n+1)(3n^2+3n-1),$$

$$S_n^5 = \frac{1}{12} n^2(n+1)^2(2n^2+2n-1),$$

$$S_n^6 = \frac{1}{42} n(n+1)(2n+1)(3n^4+6n^3-3n+1),$$

$$S_n^7 = \frac{1}{24} n^2(n+1)^2(3n^4+6n^3-n^2-4n+2),$$

$$S_n^8 = \frac{1}{90} n(n+1)(2n+1)(5n^6+15n^5+5n^4-15n^3-n^2+9n-3),$$

$$S_n^9 = \frac{1}{20} (2n^{10}+10n^9+15n^8-14n^6+10n^4-3n^2),$$

$$S_n^{10} = \frac{1}{66} (6n^{11}+33n^{10}+55n^9-66n^7+66n^5-33n^3+5n),$$

$$S_n^{11} = \frac{1}{24} (2n^{12}+12n^{11}+22n^{10}-33n^8+44n^6-33n^4+10n^2),$$

$$S_n^{12} = \frac{1}{2730} (210n^{13}+1365n^{12}+3630n^{11}-4935n^9+115n^8+9640n^7+1960n^6-5899n^5+35n^4+4550n^3+1382n^2-691n) \text{ etc.}$$

Problems.

- 1). Using the mathematical induction on the base of (1), we prove that $B_{2n-1} = 0$, if $n \geq 1$.
- 2). Prove that S_n^k is divisible by $n(n+1)$.
- 3). Prove that S_n^{2k+1} is divisible by $n^2(n+1)^2$.
- 4). Determine those natural numbers n, k for which S_n^{2k} is divisible $n(n+1)(2n+1)$.
- 5). Detach in parts the sums $S_n^9, S_n^{10}, S_n^{11}, S_n^{12}$.
- 6). Using (2), (3), compute the sums $S_n^{13}, \dots, S_n^{21}$.

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